

UNIVERSIDADE D
COIMBRA

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**AN ASSESSMENT OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY
OBLIGATIONS AS AN ENERGY POLICY
INSTRUMENT AND A PERSPECTIVE FOR 2030**

APPENDICES

Dissertação no âmbito do Mestrado em Energia para a Sustentabilidade orientada pelo Professor Doutor Álvaro Filipe Peixoto Cardoso de Oliveira Gomes e Professor Doutor António Manuel Oliveira Gomes Martins e apresentada ao Departamento de Engenharia Mecânica da Faculdade de Ciências e Tecnologia da Universidade de Coimbra.

Outubro de 2021

Faculdade de Ciências e Tecnologia da Universidade de Coimbra

An Assessment of Energy Efficiency Obligations as an Energy Policy Instrument and a Perspective for 2030

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APPENDIX A

Efficiency in Energy Use

Energy Efficiency Targets

Each Member State had to set an indicative national energy efficiency target, based on either primary or final energy consumption, primary or final energy savings, or energy intensity. Member States had to notify those targets to the Commission in accordance with Article 24(1) and Annex XIV Part 1 of the EED. When doing so, they must also express those targets in terms of an absolute level of primary energy consumption and final energy consumption in 2020 and should explain how, and base on which data, this has been calculated. It excludes deliveries to the energy transformation sector and the energy industries themselves. When setting those targets, Member States had to take into account:

- a) that the Union's 2020 energy consumption has to be no more than 1 474 Mtoe of primary energy or no more than 1 078 Mtoe of final energy;
- b) the measures provided for in the Directive;
- c) the measures adopted to reach the national energy saving targets adopted pursuant to Article 4(1) of Directive 2006/32/EC; and
- d) other measures to promote energy efficiency within Member States and at Union level.

When setting those targets, Member States might also take into account national circumstances affecting primary energy consumption, such as:

- a) remaining cost-effective energy-saving potential;
- b) GDP evolution and forecast;
- c) changes of energy imports and exports;
- d) development of all sources of renewable energies, nuclear energy, carbon capture and storage; and
- e) early action.

Building renovation

Member States had to establish a long-term strategy for mobilising investment in the renovation of the national stock of residential and commercial buildings, both public and private. This strategy should include:

- a) an overview of the national building stock based, as appropriate, on statistical sampling;
- b) identification of cost-effective approaches to renovations relevant to the building type and climatic zone;
- c) policies and measures to stimulate cost-effective deep renovations of buildings, including staged deep renovations;
- d) a forward-looking perspective to guide investment decisions of individuals, the construction industry and financial institutions;
- e) an evidence-based estimate of expected energy savings and wider benefits.

Purchasing by public bodies

Member States should ensure that central governments purchase only products, services and buildings with high energy-efficiency performance, in so far as that is consistent with cost-effectiveness, economic feasibility, wider sustainability, technical suitability, as well as sufficient competition, as referred to in Annex III.

Energy efficiency obligation Schemes

Each Member State should set up an energy efficiency obligation scheme. That scheme must ensure that energy distributors and/or retail energy sales companies that are designated as obligated parties operating in each Member State's territory achieve a cumulative end-use energy savings target by 31 December 2020.

That target had to be at least equivalent to achieving new savings each year from 1 January 2014 to 31 December 2020 of 1,5 % of the annual energy sales to final customers of all energy distributors or all retail energy sales companies by volume, averaged over the most recent three-year period prior to 1 January 2013. The sales of energy, by volume, used in transport may be partially or fully excluded from this calculation.

Member States had to decide how the calculated quantity of new savings referred to in the previous paragraph is to be phased over the period.

Energy audits and energy management systems

Member States had to promote the availability to all final customers of high-quality energy audits which are cost-effective and:

- a) carried out in an independent manner by qualified and/or accredited experts according to qualification criteria; or
- b) implemented and supervised by independent authorities under national legislation.

The energy audits may be carried out by in-house experts or energy auditors provided that the Member State concerned has put in place a scheme to assure and check their quality, including, if appropriate, an annual random selection of at least a statistically significant percentage of all the energy audits they carry out. For the purpose of guaranteeing the high quality of the energy audits and energy management systems, Member States should establish transparent and non-discriminatory minimum criteria for energy audits based on Annex VI of the Directive.

Member States have to develop programmes to encourage small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to undergo energy audits and the subsequent implementation of the recommendations from these audits.

Member States should bring to the attention of SMEs, including through their respective representative intermediary organisations, concrete examples of how energy management systems could help their businesses.

Member States should also develop programmes to raise awareness among households about the benefits of such audits through appropriate advice services.

Member States had to encourage training programmes for the qualification of energy auditors in order to facilitate sufficient availability of experts.

Member States should ensure that enterprises that are not SMEs are subject to an energy audit carried out in an independent and cost-effective manner by qualified and/or accredited experts or implemented and supervised by independent authorities under national legislation by 5 December 2015 and at least every four years from the date of the previous energy audit.

Metering and Billing information

Member States had to ensure that, in so far as it was technically possible, financially reasonable and proportionate in relation to the potential energy savings, final customers for electricity, natural gas, district heating, district cooling and domestic hot water were provided with competitively priced individual meters that accurately reflect the final customer's actual energy consumption and that provide information on actual time of use.

Such a competitively priced individual meter has always to be provided when:

- a) an existing meter is replaced, unless this is technically impossible or not cost-effective in relation to the estimated potential savings in the long term;
- b) a new connection is made in a new building or a building undergoes major renovations, as set out in Directive 2010/31/EU.

Where, and to the extent that, Member States implement intelligent metering systems and roll out smart meters for natural gas and/or electricity in accordance with Directives 2009/72/EC and 2009/73/EC, the energy efficiency directive states that:

- a) they should ensure that the metering systems provide to final customers information on actual time of use and that the objectives of energy efficiency and benefits for final customers are fully taken into account when establishing the minimum functionalities of the meters and the obligations imposed on market participants;
- b) they must ensure the security of the smart meters and data communication, and the privacy of final customers, in compliance with relevant Union data protection and privacy legislation;

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- c) in the case of electricity and at the request of the final customer, they should require meter operators to ensure that the meter or meters can account for electricity put into the grid from the final customer's premises;
 - d) they should ensure that if final customers request it, metering data on their electricity input and off-take is made available to them or to a third party acting on behalf of the final customer in an easily understandable format that they can use to compare deals on a like-for-like basis;
 - e) they should require that appropriate advice and information be given to customers at the time of installation of smart meters, in particular about their full potential with regard to meter reading management and the monitoring of energy consumption.

Where heating and cooling or hot water are supplied to a building from a district heating network or from a central source servicing multiple building, a heat or hot water meter must be installed at the heating exchanger or point of delivery.

Where final customers do not have smart meters as referred to in Directives 2009/72/EC and 2009/73/EC, Member States should ensure, by 31 December 2014, that billing information was accurate and based on actual consumption, in accordance with point 1.1 of Annex VII of the EED, for all the sectors covered by this Directive, including energy distributors, distribution system operators and retail energy sales companies, where this is technically possible and economically justified.

This obligation may be fulfilled by a system of regular self-reading by the final customers whereby they communicate readings from their meter to the energy supplier. Only when the final customer has not provided a meter reading for a given billing interval, the billing must be based on estimated consumption or a flat rate.

Meters installed in accordance with Directives 2009/72/EC and 2009/73/EC must enable accurate billing information based on actual consumption. Member States must ensure that final customers have the possibility of easy access to complementary information on historical consumption allowing detailed self- checks.

Member States must ensure that final customers receive all their bills and billing information for energy consumption free of charge and that final customers also have access to their consumption data in an appropriate way and free of charge.

Consumer information and empowering programme

Member States have to take appropriate measures to promote and facilitate an efficient use of energy by small energy customers, including domestic customers. These measures may be part of a national strategy. For this purpose, these measures must include one or more of the elements listed under point (a) or (b):

- a) a range of instruments and policies to promote behavioural change which may include:
 - i) fiscal incentives;
 - ii) access to finance, grants or subsidies;
 - iii) information provision;
 - iv) exemplary projects;
 - v) workplace activities;

- b) ways and means to engage consumers and consumer organisations during the possible roll-out of smart meters through communication of:
 - i) cost-effective and easy-to-achieve changes in energy use;
 - ii) information on energy efficiency measures.

Penalties - Member States have to lay down the rules on penalties applicable in case of non-compliance with the national provisions adopted pursuant to Articles 7 to 11 and Article 18(3) of the EED and must take the necessary measures to ensure that they are implemented. The penalties provided for have to be effective, proportionate and dissuasive. Member States have to notify those provisions to the Commission by 5 June 2014 and must notify it without delay of any subsequent amendment affecting them.

Efficiency in Energy Supply

Promotion of efficiency in heating and cooling

By 31 December 2015, Member States should carry out and notify to the Commission a comprehensive assessment of the potential for the application of high-efficiency cogeneration and efficient district heating and cooling, containing the information set out in Annex VIII. If they have already carried out an equivalent assessment, they must notify it to the Commission.

Member States must adopt policies which encourage the due taking into account at local and regional levels of the potential of using efficient heating and cooling systems, in particular those using high-efficiency cogeneration. Account should be taken of the potential for developing local and regional heat markets.

For this purpose, Member States must carry out a cost-benefit analysis covering their territory based on climate conditions, economic feasibility and technical suitability in accordance with Part 1 of Annex IX. The cost-benefit analysis should be capable of facilitating the identification of the most resource- and cost-efficient solutions to meeting heating and cooling needs.

Energy transformation, transmission and distribution

Member States had to ensure that national energy regulatory authorities pay due regard to energy efficiency in carrying out the regulatory tasks specified in Directives 2009/72/EC and 2009/73/EC regarding their decisions on the operation of the gas and electricity infrastructure.

Member States must in particular ensure that national energy regulatory authorities, through the development of network tariffs and regulations, within the framework of Directive 2009/72/EC and taking into account the costs and benefits of each measure, provide incentives for grid operators to make available system services to network users permitting them to implement energy efficiency improvement measures in the context of the continuing deployment of smart grids.

Such system services may be determined by the system operator and should not adversely impact the security of the system.

Member States should ensure, by 30 June 2015, that:

- a) an assessment is undertaken of the energy efficiency potentials of their gas and electricity infrastructure, in particular regarding transmission, distribution, load management and interoperability, and connection to energy generating installations, including access possibilities for micro energy generators;
- b) concrete measures and investments are identified for the introduction of cost-effective energy efficiency improvements in the network infrastructure, with a timetable for their introduction.

Member States may permit components of schemes and tariff structures with a social aim for net-bound energy transmission and distribution, provided that any disruptive effects on the transmission and distribution system are kept to the minimum necessary and are not disproportionate to the social aim.

Member States should ensure the removal of those incentives in transmission and distribution tariffs that are detrimental to the overall efficiency (including energy efficiency) of the generation, transmission, distribution and supply of electricity or those that might hamper participation of demand response, in balancing markets and ancillary services procurement.

Horizontal Provisions

Availability of qualification, accreditation and certification schemes

The EED issued in 2012 determined where a Member State considers that the national level of technical competence, objectivity and reliability is insufficient, it should ensure that, by 31 December 2014, certification and/or accreditation schemes and/or equivalent qualification schemes, including, where necessary, suitable training programmes, become or are available for providers of energy services, energy audits, energy managers and installers of energy-related building elements as defined in Article 2(9) of Directive 2010/31/EU.

Member States also had to ensure that the schemes provide transparency to consumers, are reliable and contribute to national energy efficiency objectives.

Information and training

Member States have to ensure that information on available energy efficiency mechanisms and financial and legal frameworks is transparent and widely disseminated to all relevant market actors, such as consumers, builders, architects, engineers, environmental and energy auditors, and installers of building elements as defined in Directive 2010/31/EU.

Member States have to encourage the provision of information to banks and other financial institutions on possibilities of participating, including through the creation of public/private partnerships, in the financing of energy efficiency improvement measures.

Member States also have to establish appropriate conditions for market operators to provide adequate and targeted information and advice to energy consumers on energy efficiency.

Energy services

Member States have to promote the energy services market and access for SMEs to this market by:

- a) disseminating clear and easily accessible information on:
 - i) available energy service contracts and clauses that should be included in such contracts to guarantee energy savings and final customers' rights;
 - ii) financial instruments, incentives, grants and loans to support energy efficiency service projects;
- b) encouraging the development of quality labels, inter alia, by trade associations;
- c) making publicly available and regularly updating a list of available energy service providers who are qualified and/or certified and their qualifications and/or certifications in accordance with Article 16, or providing an interface where energy service providers can provide information;
- d) supporting the public sector in taking up energy service offers, in particular for building refurbishment, by:

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- i) providing model contracts for energy performance contracting which include at least the items listed in Annex XIII of the EED;
 - ii) providing information on best practices for energy performance contracting, including, if available, cost- benefit analysis using a life-cycle approach;
 - e) providing a qualitative review in the framework of the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan regarding the current and future development of the energy services market.

Energy Efficiency Nacional Fund, Financing and Technical Support

Without prejudice to Articles 107 and 108 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, Member States should facilitate the establishment of financing facilities, or use of existing ones, for energy efficiency improvement measures to maximise the benefits of multiple streams of financing.

Member States may set up an Energy Efficiency National Fund. The purpose of this fund should be to support national energy efficiency initiatives.

Member States may allow for the obligations set out in Article 5(1) to be fulfilled by annual contributions to the Energy Efficiency National Fund of an amount equal to the investments required to achieve those obligations.

Member States may provide that obligated parties can fulfil their obligations set out in Article 7(1) by contributing annually to the Energy Efficiency National Fund an amount equal to the investments required to achieve those obligations.

Review and monitoring of implementation

By 30 April each year as from 2013, Member States have to report on the progress achieved towards national energy efficiency targets, in accordance with Part 1 of Annex XIV. The report may form part of the National Reform Programmes referred to in Council Recommendation 2010/410/EU of 13 July 2010 on broad guidelines for the economic policies of the Member States and of the Union.

By 30 April 2014, and every three years thereafter, Member States must submit National Energy Efficiency Action Plans. The National Energy Efficiency Action Plans are due to cover significant energy efficiency improvement measures and expected and/ or achieved energy savings, including those in the supply, transmission and distribution of energy as well as energy end-use, in view of achieving the national energy efficiency targets referred to in Article 3(1) of the EED. The National Energy Efficiency Action Plans should be complemented with updated estimates of expected overall primary energy consumption in 2020, as well as estimated levels of primary energy consumption in the sectors indicated in Part 1 of Annex XIV.

APPENDIX B

Portugal Annual Reports Data

				reporting year 2011	reporting year 2012	reporting year 2013	reporting year 2014	reporting year 2015	reporting year 2016	reporting year 2017	reporting year 2018
	AR INDICATOR	EUROSTAT INDICATOR	UNIT	AMOUNT							
1	(i) primary energy consumption	Primary Energy Consumption	Ktoe	20 759,0	20 197,0	21 278,2	20 700,0	21 700,0	22 100,0	22 492,0	22 631,0
2	(ii) total final energy consumption	Final Energy Consumption	Ktoe	16 913,0	15 591,0	15 893,2	15 807,0	16 037,0	16 110,1	15 613,0	16 908,0
3	iii) final energy consumption - industry	Final Energy Consumption - Industry	Ktoe	5 703,0	5 061,0	4 588,2	4 403,0	4 450,0	4 331,8	4 883,0	4 571,0
4	(iii) final energy consumption - transport	Final Energy Consumption - Transport	Ktoe	6 047,0	5 568,0	6 385,8	6 472,0	6 613,0	6 769,9	5 805,0	7 223,0
5	final energy consumption in pipeline transport	Consumption in Pipeline transport	Ktoe			0,8	1,0	1,0	0,5		
6	(iii) final energy consumption - households	Residential	Ktoe	2 801,0	2 657,0	2 639,7	2 570,0	2 539,0	2 620,7	2 562,0	2 654,0
7	(iii) final energy consumption - services	Services	Ktoe	1 918,0	1 868,0	1 779,3	1 905,0	1 960,0	1 938,2	1 903,0	1 968,0
8	final energy consumption - agriculture	Agriculture/Forestry	Ktoe			329,5	338,0	345,0	341,9	371,0	382,0
9	final energy consumption – other sectors	Other sectors	Ktoe			4 872,7	4 931,0	35,0	5 008,4	88,0	110,0
10	(iv) gross value added - industry	Industry (except construction)	Million euro, chain-linked volumes,	21 626,0	26 527,0	23 552,2	23 279,0		24 637,6	33 654,0	24 977,0

		Construction	reference year 2005 (at 2005 exchange rates)			5 012,0	5 488,0		5 008,8		
11	(iv) gross value added - services	Wholesale and retail trade, transport, accomodation and food service activities	Million euro, chain-linked volumes, reference year 2005 (at 2005 exchange rates)	97 344,0	103 310,0	33 228,4	33 582,0		36 833,9	120 317,0	114 169,0
		Information and communication				5 761,3	5 832,0		5 887,0		
		Financial and insurance activities				9 480,9	9 387,0		8 309,5		
		Real estates activities				12 936,1	13 024,0		13 259,8		
		Professional, scientific and technical activities; administrative and support services activities				9 570,3	9 970,0		10 984,7		
		Public administration, defence, education human health and social work activities				29 342,3	28 961,0		29 354,8		
		Arts, entertainment and recreation; other service activities; activities of household and extra-territorial organizations and bodies				4 065,5	3 967,0		4 154,6		
12	(v) disposable income for households	Disposable income, gross	Million euro, current prices	125 024,0	122 851,0	121 997,0	n.a			151 522,0	124 272,0
13	(vi) gross domestic product (GDP)	Gross domestic product at market prices	Million euro, chain-linked volumes, reference year 2005 (at 2005 exchange rates)	171 065,0	155 717,0	149 374,0	n.a		174 978,0	179 915,0	198 119,0
14	(vii) electricity generation from	Gross electricity generation Main activity electricity only - Nuclear	ktoe	22442 (GWh)	29155 (GWh)					2 683,0	2 157,0

thermal power generation	Gross electricity generation Main activity CHP plants - Nuclear								
	Gross electricity generation Autoproducer electricity only - Nuclear								
	Gross electricity generation Autoproducer CHP plants - Nuclear								
	Gross electricity generation Main activity electricity only - Geothermal				16,9	17,6	18,0	14,8	
	Gross electricity generation Main activity electricity only - Combustible Fuels				1 301,6	1 301,0	1 882,0	1 884,1	
	Gross electricity generation Main activity electricity only - Other Sources								
	Gross electricity generation Main activity CHP plants - Geothermal								
	Gross electricity generation Main activity CHP plants - Combustible Fuels				16,5	16,5	17,0	16,5	
	Gross electricity generation Main activity CHP plants - Other Sources								
	Gross electricity generation Main activity electricity only - Solar Thermal								
	Gross electricity generation Autoproducer electricity only - Geothermal								
	Gross electricity generation Autoproducer electricity only - Combustible Fuels				78,3	71,0	82,0	85,1	
	Gross electricity generation Autoproducer electricity only - Heat from Chemical Sources								

		Gross electricity generation Autoproducer electricity only - Other Sources									
		Gross electricity generation Autoproducer CHP plants - Geothermal									
		Gross electricity generation Autoproducer CHP plants - Combustible Fuels				676,6	627,0	600,0	585,5		
		Gross electricity generation Autoproducer CHP plants - Heat from Chemical Sources				0,3	1,0	1,0	1,0		
		Gross electricity generation Autoproducer CHP plants - Other Sources									
		Gross electricity generation Autoproducer electricity only - Solar Thermal									
		TOTAL	ktoe	1 929,7	2 506,9	2 090,2	2 034,1	2 600,0	2 587,0	2 683,0	2 157,0
15	(viii) electricity generation from CHP	Gross electricity generation Main activity CHP plants - Nuclear									
		Gross electricity generation Autoproducer CHP plants - Nuclear									
		Gross electricity generation Main activity CHP plants - Geothermal									
		Gross electricity generation Main activity CHP plants - Combustible Fuels	ktoe	8255(GWh)	7573(GWh)	16,5	16,5	17,0	16,5	615,0	609,0
		Gross electricity generation Main activity CHP plants - Other Sources									
		Gross electricity generation Autoproducer CHP plants - Geothermal									
		Gross electricity generation Autoproducer CHP plants - Combustible Fuels				676,7	626,6	600,0	585,5		

		Gross electricity generation Autoproducer CHP plants - Heat from Chemical Sources				0,3	0,6	1,0			
		Gross electricity generation Autoproducer CHP plants - Other Sources									
		TOTAL	ktoe	709,0	651,2	693,5	643,7	618,0	602,0	615,0	609,0
16	(ix) heat generation from thermal power generation	Gross heat production Main activity CHP plants - Nuclear	ktoe								
		Gross heat production Main activity heat only plants - Nuclear									
		Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Nuclear									
		Gross heat production Autoproducer heat only plants - Nuclear									
		Gross heat production Main activity CHP plants - Geothermal									
		Gross heat production Main activity CHP plants - Combustible Fuels				0,8	0,8	1,0	0,8		
		Gross heat production Main activity CHP plants - Heat Pumps									
		Gross heat production Main activity CHP plants - Electric Boilers									
		Gross heat production Main activity CHP plants - Other Sources									
		Gross heat production Main activity CHP plants - Solar									
		Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Geothermal									
		Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Combustible Fuels						608,8	509,5	468,0	449,3

	Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Heat Pumps										
	Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Electric Boilers										
	Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Heat from Chemical Sources			1,1	1,3	2,0					
	Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Other Sources										
	Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Solar										
	Gross heat production Main activity heat only plants - Geothermal										
	Gross heat production Main activity heat only plants - Solar										
	Gross heat production Main activity heat only plants - Combustible Fuels										
	Gross heat production Main activity heat only plants - Heat Pumps										
	Gross heat production Main activity heat only plants - Electric Boilers										
	Gross heat production Main activity heat only plants - Other Sources										
	Gross heat production Autoproducer heat only plants - Geothermal										
	Gross heat production Autoproducer heat only plants - Solar										
	Gross heat production Autoproducer heat only plants - Combustible Fuels										

		Gross heat production Autoproducer heat only plants - Heat Pumps									
		Gross heat production Autoproducer heat only plants - Electric Boilers									
		Gross heat production Autoproducer heat only plants - Heat from Chemical Sources									
		Gross heat production Autoproducer heat only plants - Other Sources									
		TOTAL	ktoe			610,7	511,6	471,0	450,1		
17	Waste heat produced in industrial installations	ESTAT data not available. Please, provide national data with definitions/explanations in column K.				n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
18	(x) heat generation from CHP	Gross heat production Main activity CHP plants - Nuclear	ktoe	20596(TJ)	21419(TJ)					456,0	1 378,0
		Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Nuclear									
		Gross heat production Main activity CHP plants - Geothermal									
		Gross heat production Main activity CHP plants - Combustible Fuels				0,8	0,8	1,0	0,8		
		Gross heat production Main activity CHP plants - Heat Pumps									
		Gross heat production Main activity CHP plants - Electric Boilers									
		Gross heat production Main activity CHP plants - Other Sources									
		Gross heat production Main activity CHP plants - Solar									

		Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Geothermal									
		Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Combustible Fuels				608,8	509,5	468,0	449,3		
		Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Heat Pumps									
		Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Electric Boilers									
		Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Heat from Chemical Sources				1,1	1,3	2,0			
		Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Other Sources									
		Gross heat production Autoproducer CHP plants - Solar									
		TOTAL	ktoe	491,9	511,6	610,7	511,6	471,0	450,1	456,0	1 378,0
19	Waste heat recovered from industrial installations	ESTAT data not available. Please, provide national data with definitions/explanations in column K.				n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
20	(xi) fuel input for thermal power generation	Transformation input - Nuclear Power Stations	ktoe								
		Transformation input - Conventional Thermal Power Stations		4 621,0	4 592,0	5 540,5	5 488,0	6 654,0	6 525,2	7 648,0	7 641,0
		Transformation input - District Heating Plants									
21	(xii) passenger kilometres (pkm)	Railway TRA_COV: Total transport	Millions of passenger- kilometres		9 885,0	3 646,0	3 852,0	17 240,0	n.a		102,17*10 ⁹
		Road VEHICLE: Total	Millions of passenger- kilometres			n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a		

22	passenger kilometres (pkm)	Domestic Maritime: ESTAT data not available. Please, provide national data with definitions/explanations in column K.	Millions of Tonne-kilometre			n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a		
23	passenger kilometres (pkm)	Total Aviation National: ESTAT data not available. Please, provide national data with definitions/explanations in column K.	Millions of Tonne-kilometre			n.a	2 543,0	2 096,0	n.a		
24	passenger kilometres (pkm)	Total Aviation International: ESTAT data not available. Please, provide national data with definitions/explanations in column K.	Millions of Tonne-kilometre			n.a	32 350,0	31 942,0	n.a		
25	(xiii) tonnes kilometres (tkm)	Railway TRA_COV: Total transport	Millions of Tonne-kilometre	37 472,0	32 188,0	2 290,0	2 434,0	2 688,0	n.a	36,01*10^9	
		Road TRA_OPER: Total - Total transport	Millions of Tonne-kilometre			148 177,0	34 863,0	31 835,0	n.a		
		Waterway TRA_COV: Total transport	Millions of Tonne-kilometre			n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a		
26	tonnes kilometres (tkm)	Domestic Maritime: ESTAT data not available. Please, provide national data with definitions/explanations in column K.	Millions of Tonne-kilometre			n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a		
27	tonnes kilometres (tkm)	Total Aviation National: ESTAT data not available. Please, provide national data with definitions/explanations in column K.	Millions of Tonne-kilometre			n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a		
28	tonnes kilometres (tkm)	Total Aviation International: ESTAT data not available. Please, provide national data with	Millions of Tonne-kilometre			n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a		

		definitions/explanations in column K.									
29	(xv) population	Population on 1 January - total	Persons	10 562 000,0	10 487 000,0	10 427 301,0	10 427 301,0	10 374 822,0	10 341 330,0	10 291 027,0	10 276 617,0
30	Total number of households	ESTAT data not available. Please, provide national data with definitions/explanations in column K.	Householders			n.a	5 936 689,0	5 926 286,0	n.a	n.a	n.a
31	Energy transmission and distribution losses (all fuels)	Distribution Losses	ktoe	4088(GWh)	4708(GWh)	473,8	452,0	429,0	427,9	445,0	442,0
32	Heat generation from district heating plants	Transformation output - District Heating Plants	ktoe			0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
33	Fuel input in district heating plants	Transformation input - District Heating Plants	ktoe			0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0

EED. (2012). *Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on energy efficiency. October 2012, 1–56.*